

Adult Education for Effective Community Engagement in Civic and Democratic Processes: Issues and Challenges

Goodness Philip Woha (PhD) & ²Sonia Nada Olomi

Department of Adult Education and Community Development.

Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

Corresponding Authors' Email: goodness.wohaphilip@iaue.edu.ng & nada.olomi@iaue.edu.ng

Abstract

The paper identified adult education as an effective tool for enhancing civic compliance among adult citizens in Nigeria, its issues and challenges. The paper pointed out importance of adult education in promoting civic engagement to include that it provides platform and avenue through which adults are reached and educated on community engagement in civic processes. It identified poverty, religious and social class boundaries, high rate of illiteracy as contributors, marginalization, electoral violence, political fraud, insecurity and so on as contributors of civic apathy. The paper pointed out benefits of effective community engagement in civic processes such as, sustained democracy, peace and unity, sustainable community development programmes, accountability on the part of the leaders, political stability etc. Among adult education programmes identified for effective community engagement in civic processes include community education, adult civic education, mass literacy education and political \ leadership education. This paper identified limited access to adult education programmes, low level of illiteracy, lack of civic knowledge, funding constraints, and lack of awareness as issues and challenges limiting actualization of improvement in civic and democratic engagement. It suggests that there should be room for improved funding, collaboration with governmental, NGOs and CBOs for improved resource mobilization and training of facilitators to be abreast with global best practices for effectiveness of the process.

Keywords: Adult Education, Effective Community Engagement, Civic and Democratic Processes, Issues and Challenges

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria gained independence in 1960 and later became a republic in 1963; ever since, Nigeria has been a democratic nation from 1960 at independence till 1966 after the military breach of democratic government through a coup – de – tat. Nigeria, attempted another democratic rule from 1979 to 1983 when a military junta took over power forcefully. Duru (2017), explained this as a perpetual state of transition. Duru, further stated that after independence in 1960, there were a series of political transitions, from parliamentary democracy to military rule Omotola (2010), stated that the political atmosphere in the country remained unstable until the death of General Sani Abacha in 1999 which birth the stay of democracy in Nigeria.

Olaleye and Ayobade (2021), described Nigerian democracy as a “roller coaster”, as it rides from civilian to military back to civilian administration again. The post – independence era in Nigeria was occasioned by incessant encroachment on democracy which restricted citizens’ rights and privileges. Once the fundamental human rights of the people are infringed upon, governance is in jeopardy. The forceful seizure of power undemocratic dictatorship events that constitutes

military birth or triggered the quest for a democratic rule. This hunger for democracy was filled through the May, 1999 election that led to the emergence of democratic stability. Nigeria has so far, managed to maintain democratic governance from 1999 till date (2025), as a result of civilian-to-civilian transmission of power without military interruption. Which is a welcome development and must be considered a feat before contemporary African nations.

However, several scholars have viewed Nigerian practice of democracy in different ways. For instance, Onyenemezu (2012), described Nigerian democracy as a “nascent democracy”. He further stated that Nigeria is practicing what is called a “home grown democracy”, regarded as a learning process by both the leaders and the led. Adelekan and Ashibi (2021), moved further to state that Nigeria is practicing a “pretentious democracy”, where citizens’ rights are deliberately infringed upon, giving room for non-respect for the rule of law, lack of accountability and electoral credibility. In the same vein, Adewale (2019), opined that Nigeria democracy is at a “fragile state”, where citizens participation in decision making is still very frail. Also, Muse (2016), described Nigerian

democracy as an “emerging democracy” so did Adekola and Nwogu (2017), where both the leaders and masses are struggling to fit into the tenets of democracy.

Consequently, Nigerian transition from military rule to civilian rule held high hopes and expectations. Citizens looked forward to a new era of renewed hope for peace and national unity, religious tolerance, rapid socio- economic development, electoral stability, respect for rule of law and sovereignty amongst others. However, as against the expectations of the masses, are what Duru (2017), pointed out to be incidents of political turbulence, along with communal and religious violence across the country. More to these are political agitations for division from various regions of the nation. Militancy at the South-South Niger Delta region, IPOB agitation at the South East, Boko Haram insurgency, herdsmen and farmers clashes at the Northern region of the country. All of these can be linked to apathy occasioned by marginalization, corrupt practices and “rape of democracy”. In the same vein, Goodluck Jonathan Foundation (GTF) (2021), opined that the return to democratic rule in 1999 was rapped with high hopes, majority of Nigerians felt that rule will allow for informed decisions in governance that will lead to a better living condition. Though, they asserted that democratic experiment in the fourth republic provides opportunity for the masses to be involved in governance as the true state of democracy. Representative and participatory democracy as the general view of Nigerian democracy (Muse 2016). The masses, grassroot or community participation must be considered in order to build and sustain democracy.

Regrettably, the act of voluntary, active, popular participation in civic processes which was the norm before and in the post – independence era is swiftly drifting away as Goodluck Jonathan Foundation (2021), records that there was low turnout of voters in Edo and Ondo States in 2019 and 2021 respectively. Based on this backdrop, the need for adult education to rekindle effective community engagement in civic processes in Nigeria. To back up this is Koku (2017), who stated that, in order to restore political stability in Nigeria, it is important to educate Nigerians to consider the country first in whatever they are doing before any other personal interest.

Civic/Democratic Process and Community Engagement in Nigeria

Civic or democratic process is a systematic and well-planned road map of a particular people on who, how and means of governance. Democracy and civic process hand and hand. Both terms are co-joined twin that can be separated. According to Robert, as sited in Githinji (2021), Civic process is the act of consciously and systematically interpreting and implementing democratic rules. He further stated that, it is the way people set up agencies and rules to govern themselves.

A thorough, democracy, involves two stages which include:

1. The setting of agenda which is the policy formation stage.
2. The decisive stage where policies are implemented, reviewed for adoption or rejection.

Civic process as defined by Mc Bride in Jones (2016), focuses on two major components which are;

1. Political activities (Voting, Campaigning)
2. Social activities (Belonging to a party and involving in civil activisms)

Humans are social beings and a political in nature because of the tendency to lead and direct activities and events as they relate and affects man.

Consequently, community engagement in a democratic process is described as the interests, activities involvement of people at the grassroot in the day to day running of government. Different scholars have described these activities in different ways;

For instance, Muse (2019), called it public participation, Gaventa and Valderramma in Muse (2017), calls it political participation and community social project, participation; Bierele and Cayford calls it voters’ participation. Others has also, referred it to mean public participation and citizens participation. However, all these are structured to achieve popular participation of the people in their own governance. Muse (2017), further explained that all these postulations are related to those actives through which political parties, civil society, labour unions, traditional leaders, academics, religious groups, student associations, community-based organizations and

other stakeholders or leaders directly or indirectly and in the formation of public policy for good governance.

At this juncture, it is pertinent to look into the meaning of a community. A community is a group of people who are brought together by a common value, interest, geographical location or experience. While community engagement according to Nwaugo (2020), is the process of working collaboratively as a group or affiliates to pool latent resources in addressing a common concern.

Just like other third world countries that are new at democracy, Nigeria as a nation is faced with lots of challenges especially, at the decisive stage of democratic process. The issue of voter apathy is one of the challenges threatening the nation's democracy in this regards Onyenemezu (2012), Posits that events from the unfair annulment of June, 12 presidential election of 1993 allegedly won by Chief M.K.O. Abiola had caused a shiver in the masses and since then, has been a part of the masses. Community engagement as a conscious, deliberate, purposeful, self-willed involvement of members of a particular community in proffering solutions to their communal challenges and decision making, indicates that community's participation must not be out of compulsion rather should be spurred out of self-will as stated by Akinleye (2023).

Need for Effective Community Engagement in Civic Processes in Nigeria.

The complexity of the aftermath and scope of any civic process makes effective community engagement a pivot for sustained democracy. The aftermath of a civic process might be negative or positive and comes back to "make" or "mar" the society. Thereafter, it becomes necessary to key into community engagement for its divers scope as it relates to almost every aspect of community life such as environment and health, socio-cultural concerns, leadership and politics, family life etc.

Succinctly, the rationale for effective community engagement is hinged on the need for practice, promotion, preservation and sustainability of democracy. Every other factor are products of "true democracy" and rule of law. Democracy as defined by Unal and Kaygin (2019), is that system that enables citizens to exercise political structure that is

open to public participation and electoral rights and freedoms. Democracy as generally asserted as the government of the people, for the people, and by the people, gives credence to the community as the nucleus of democracy. In the same vein, Adelekan and Ashibi (2020), described democracy as a system of government based on the acquisition of authority from the people, the institutionalization of the rule of law, the emphasis on the legitimacy of rulers, the availability of choices and cherished values including freedom, transparency and accountability. Given that the ideology of democracy is people- centered, Adekola and Nwogu (2015), opined that whatever that is done in a democratic government should start with the people and end with the people.

Further benefits of inclusive citizen's participation in democratic processes are;

1. Improved citizens' trust and confidence on the leaders.
2. Increase in the level of accountability by public office holders. Community members' involvement in civic processes will force office holders to become accountable to the masses. Adebowale and Olaleye (2021), holds the view that when large number of persons play active role in civic processes, the representatives become conscious of the need to be accountable to their electorates.
3. It will be a model to create checks and balances in democracy. Adewale (2019), identified the need to promote proper regulation and fair ground for all through civic participation.
4. Effective community engagement in civic processes will lead to political stability and peace. Effective community engagement will curtail most of the existing conflicts and terrorist attacks in the country. It will dampen the agitations and quest for division. In line with this is Ojo and Ako (2021).
5. Sustained community development programmes are another need for the engagement of community members in democratic processes as Nyerere in Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008), asserts that there is a bridge between democracy and

community development, which is humans. He further stated that development is of man, by man and for man. Therefore, the need to include community members in civic processes by creating an enabling environment that will encourage community participation in civic processes.

In Dokubo and Elemuwa (2021), they opined that the creation of local governments serves as vital tool for speeding-up the pace of socio-economic development. However, local government as a grassroot government must ensure that governmental policies and development projects even the strategies must have a “human face” by taking through the bottom top approach in ensuring effective community engagement in Nigeria.

Factors that Militate against Community Engagement in Civic Processes in Nigeria

Despite the fact that civic participation is a viable tool in nations’ building, yet, history of elections and other civic engagements records backdrop. Muse and Narsiah (2015), attributes the persistent emasculation of public participation in Nigeria to the processes of state formation in the colonial and post-colonial era. This assertion can be said to be true as the political entity known as Nigeria was birth out of forceful amalgamation in 1914 by Lord Fredrick Lugard. However, other factors include;

Cultural, group, class and ethnic boundaries Joseph (2014), stated that these factors are capable of preventing people from actively participating in civic processes. Peoples’ determination to take active part in civic processes is majorly beckoned on these factors. For instance, the “Muslim – Muslim” presidential ticket of 2023 attracted lots of attention so also the crises that rocked the Peoples Democratic Party PDP was partly issues of ethnic batten of power among the party leadership. This, of course can lead to apathy as electorates will always prefer to vote in candidates of same ties.

Poverty is another challenge to effective community engagement in civic processes. This is because the widespread poverty has left citizens to prioritize engagement in civic processes to making ends meet.

High rate of illiteracy especially, in the area of citizenship and political literacy. Jones (2016),

pointed out that most citizens of voting age are illiterates as such, does not have any proper knowledge about their civic rights and duties due to alphabetic illiteracy and neo-colonial perception of governance.

Others as pointed out by Shaw and Crowther (2013) are;

- (1) Disadvantaged sections of the society.
- (2) Uneven distribution of resources.
- (3) Social and educational and political marginalization.

In the same vein, Adelekan and Ashibi (2020), stated some impediments to citizens engagement in civic processes as;

- Rigging [electoral fraud].
- Electoral violence before, during and after elections.
- Lack of confidence in political leaders.

Onigiobi, Obadiora and Oriowo (2020), stated that lack of INEC machinery for intensive supervision of electoral processes, lack of freedom to participate in electoral processes, the bane of “stomach infrastructure” and impositions of candidates as factors affecting citizens’ participation in elections in Nigeria.

More to these are lack of respect for the rule of law and democratic authoritarianism, insecurity and government inability to protect lives and properties. Examples are the “End SARS protest” that changed to “Lekki massacre” in 2020 and deaths and destruction of properties that was recorded during and after 2023 presidential election in some parts of Rivers state which made the electorates to shrink to their shells during the gubernatorial elections are deterrents to effective community engagement in civic processes in Nigeria.

Promoting Effective Community Engagement in Civic Processes through Adult Education

It is pertinent to look into the definition of adult education in order to get a better knowledge of the paper.

The Concept of Adult Education

Adult education has no generally accepted definition. It has been defined differently by various scholars according to their cultural backgrounds and experiences. Given that, Nzeneri, in Nzeneri (2013), defined adult education as any kind of education given to adults based on their social,

cultural, political, economic needs to enable them adjust fully to changes and challenges in their lives and society. In line with this, Anyanwu, in Onyeozu and Okorie (2018), considers adult education as all inclusive pattern of adult development which have in view the needs of adults not only as individuals but also as members of his community and which help them to live more effectively in their society. The above definitions places adult education at the center of meeting needs and readjustments. However, adult education with its myriad of programmes wired to meet needs becomes requisite in promoting effective community engagement in civic processes in Nigeria.

Forms of adult education are,

- (1) Formal adult education- this include any form of organized education within the conventional school setting.
- (2) Non-formal adult education-these are organized training or education outside the formal school setting. Such as workshops, trainings, seminars, trainings and conferences.
- (3) Informal adult education- this Is any unplanned learning. It is also known as accidental learning. It can take place anywhere at any time. Through the radio, television, social and religious places etc. However, adult education programmes for effective community engagement include;
 - (1) Adult civic education.
 - (2) Mass literacy education.
 - (3) Community education.
 - (4) Political \ leadership education.

Adult Civic Education: This programme is tailored towards promoting civic knowledge, skills and ethical behaviour that fosters active participation in civic duties. Altaaany and Abdelbary (2024), opined that adult civic education plays vital role in social stabilization in the society. When the people are informed, they become empowered to take active part at the grassroot level. In line with this grain of thought is Finkel (2014), who asserts that adult civic education has meaningful and relatively long-lasting effects in terms of increasing political information, fostering empowerment and promoting local-level participation.

Mass Literacy Adult Education: different types of literacy programmes are embedded in this. Citizens are exposed to basic skills that enable them read, comprehend, analyze, review, criticize and utilize information that are relevant to their socio-political context. It will promote critical thinking and enable them make informed decisions concerning their participation and engagement in political policies and activities. Among the literacy programmes that will promote civic participation include; basic literacy, functional literacy and more importantly, digital literacy. Digital literacy plays significant role in enhancing easy access to dissemination and accessing of information and utilization of digital tools especially, in performing civic duties such as voting exercises.

Community Education: participating in civic duties involves a level of confidence, a sense of belonging and spirit of patriotism. This programme empowers dwellers to take part in issues that concerns them, impact in them necessary skills that promotes proper need identification, assessment and evaluation. Also build human resources who will become active and knowledgeable representative of the people.

Political/ Leadership Education: In participatory democracy, a leader must be exposed to the guiding principles of leadership, become knowledgeable of responsibilities binding a leader and relationship between a leader and the citizens. Imhangbe (2022), points out leadership education as a targeted learning engagement in leadership concept, conception and practice, a specialized learning for the understanding of leadership composition, concept and function. In Nigeria, there is need to properly orient and re-orient the leaders. This will contribute to accountability, credibility and transparency in the part of the leader. Effective leadership builds hope and promotes citizens' interest in civic and democratic processes in the society.

Issues and Challenges of Adult Education Towards Actualization of Effective Community Engagement in Civic Processes

Despite the indispensable benefits of adult education in promoting effective community engagement in civic and democratic processes,

there are several challenges and issues limiting the pace of the programme. Such include;

- 1) **Limited Access to adult education programmes** as stated Eheazu (2018). This issue is mostly affected by people in the rural communities.
- 2) **Low Literacy Level:** This can hinder citizens' ability to participate in civic processes. According to UNESCO (2017), High level of illiteracy scares people away from democratic processes as a result of lack of confidence, gap in communication and digital divide.
- 3) **Lack of Civic Knowledge:** Akinyemi (2019), stated that lack of knowledge of civic and democratic processes makes it difficult for them to get involved actively and patriotically.
- 4) **Disengagement:** According to Bhattacharya (2020), some adults feel disengaged from civic and democratic processes due to feeling of powerlessness and lack of representation.
- 5) **Funding Constraints:** Most adult education programmes are poorly sponsored especially, in Third World Countries like Nigeria. Torres (2018), opined that inadequate funding limits the reach and effectiveness of adult education activities.

CONCLUSION

Adult education plays a crucial role in promoting effective community engagement in civic and democratic processes. Adult education programmes if well harnessed, will bring about positive change in their perception towards involvement in civic processes, improved confidence in leadership, promote accountability, social cohesion, political stability and sustained development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Hence, this paper recommends the following for effective actualization of adult education programme for effective civic and democratic participation;

1. The government and non- governmental bodies should increase funding for adult education programmes to enhance their effectiveness and sustainability.
2. Efforts should be made in the training and retraining of facilitators to be abreast with global best practices.

3. There should be a synergy between the government, NGOs and Community Based organizations in order to leverage larger resources.

References

- Adekola, O., & Nwogu, G. A. (2015). Challenges of community development in an emerging democracy: Implication for adult and non-formal education. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(6), 455–466.
- Ajaps, O. S., & Obiagu, A. N. (2021). Increasing engagement through civic education: A critical consciousness theory perspective. *Journal of Culture and Values in Education*, 4(1), 64–87.
- Akinleye, M. O. (2023). The push and pull factors affecting youth engagement in politics in Nigeria. *Civic Nigeria*. <https://www.civcnigeria.org/2023eletions>
- Crowder, M. (2013). Quality standards: Integration within a bereavement environment. *The TQM Journal*, 25(1), 18–28.
- Dokubo, C., Ebinabo, F. M., & Egumah, C. S. (2021). Influence of community development on infrastructural development projects in Emohua and Ikwerre LGAs of Rivers State. *Rivers State University Journal of Education*, 24(1), 79–89.
- Duru, A. (2017). Measuring citizens' attitude towards civic and political participation in Nigeria: A descriptive approach. *Africology: The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 10(2), 35–51.
- Eheazu, C. L., & Joseph, A. (2018). Non-formal environmental adult education strategies and communication techniques for addressing environmental degradation and social policy. *Journal of Social Science*, 5(2), 52–59.
- Finkel, S. E. (2014). The impact of adult civic education programmes in developing democracy. *Journal of Public*

- Administration and Development*, 34(3), 169–181.
- Jones, A. L. (2016). The importance of civic and social engagement in minority communities. *Journal of Family Strength*, 16(1), 10–28.
- Muse, S. A., & Narsiah, S. (2015). The politics of participatory budgeting in Nigeria: A case study of community development associations. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 50(3), 263–269.
- Ojo, A., & Benjamine, I. A. (2021). The effects of citizens' enlightenment on community participation in development in Anambra State, Nigeria. *IJMSSPCS Online Journal*, 4(1), 2682–6127.
- Olayele, Y. L., & Ayobade, A. (2021). Awareness and utilization of citizenship participation for good governance in Nigeria. *Global Advanced Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 1(7), 405–427.
- Omotola, J. S., & Aiyedogbon, G. (2021). Political participation and voters' turnout in Nigeria's 2015 elections. *Journal of African Elections*, 11(1), 54–73.
- Onigiobi, O., Obadiora, A. J., & Oriowo, T. (2020). Electioneering in Nigeria: Citizens' knowledge of responsibility and engagement. *Journal of Social Studies*, 22(1), 31–50.
- Onyenemezu, C. E., & Aduvo, R. (2014). Utilization of adult continuing education programmes for sustainable national development. *International Journal of Development and Emerging Economies*, 2(1), 1–7.
- Unal, F., & Kaygin, H. (2019). Citizenship education for adults for sustainable democratic societies. *Journal of Sustainability*, 12(1), 1–19.